

Women Empowerment: An Analysis of B R Ambedkar's Contribution to India

P. Vijayakumar^{#1}, Dr. J. Thirumal^{*2},

#Department of Philosophy, Annamalai University

** Associate Professor, Department of Philosophy, Annamalai University*

Abstract— *There is no tool for development more valuable than the empowerment of women (Kofi Annan)*

An innovative figure, a pioneer of social justice, and a good reformer, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's position is noteworthy in shaping the social, political, and civic contour of India and promoting the progression of society in general and women in particular. His suffering as a Dalit and his experience with Western ideas and rational thinking built in him the assurance to confront the orthodox Hindu social order and rebuild the society along with the ideas of equality, liberty, fraternity, and respect for the pride of all including the womenfolk. He apprehended Manu liable for all troubles and suffering of women. He also held responsible the Hindu social order for assigning a stereotypical role to women. He strongly alleged that the annihilation of the wicked gender relations and uplifting the status of women was the vital necessities of the development of social reconstruction that he aimed at. Therefore, he untiringly fought for the insertion of the rights of women in different spheres of life. He awakened in women the passion to struggle for social justice and their rights through his speeches, thoughts, and reforms. His reformative measures came in the form of the Hindu Code Bill to renovate the Hindu society which became unmatched in its importance. Here is an endeavor to develop an analytical framework to measure his contribution as a warrior for women's rights.

Keywords: *Awareness, Rights, reformative initiatives, Women education, Women empowerment, Privileged, Social Reformer.*

INTRODUCTION

"We shall see better days soon and our progress will be accelerated if male education is persuaded side by side with female education." - Dr. Bhim Roa Ambedkar

Empowerment refers to the increase in the social, spiritual, political, or economic power of individuals and peoples of India. Women empowerment, independence, and improvement in their social, political, economic and health status are both essential for achieving an important end. The role played by Dr. Bhim.Roa Ambedkar as a chairperson of the constitution drafting committee has left an impression on the country's social embroidery after independence, shaping India's socio-political fabric today. It is a possibility in a different India, a very inequitable and unjust one without it. He tried to structure the moral and social foundations of India for a political order of a new and constitutional democracy committed by inherited or existing social relations from the past. Ambedkar held the highest educational credentials as an Indian of his time, and his scholarship has been widely recognized. All this is known to Dr. Ambedkar is the father of the

Indian constitution. After reading some books on it, their works, and his approach towards India, it will be clear that he is a versatile genius on his own and was also a good teacher, effective lawyer, devoted leader, committed writer, distinguished educationist, social rebel, powerful debater. He was authoritative, a Constitutionalist, a competent administrator, liberal emancipator, master statesman, and fearless fighter for the desperate masses' free and human rights.

Dr. Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar was born on 14 April 1891 at Mahov, the military cantonment was then a city in the central province of India. His father, Ram Ji Sakpal Malogya was a 'sabaydar' in the army, and his mother was 'Bhimabai Sakpal' was a housewife. Babasaheb belonged to a minor caste namely 'Mehar' which was treated as untouchables. As his father was an army officer, he was capable to arrange good education for his children, despite much resistance in India. Ambedkar was considered untouchable at school like other children Dalits. They were not acceptable to sit among the children of another so-called upper caste, and drinking water from a normal water vessel was not permitted to lower cast people like Dr. Babasaheb Bhimrao Ji. He was very appreciable in his studies. After completing his early education in Bombay, he moved to America for graduate studies and research. At Columbia University, New York he did graduation and doctorate. He also studied at the London school of the UK in economics and completed his master's and doctorate from there.

OBJECTIVES, METHODS, AND RESOURCES

The present paper is an attempt to highlight the views of Dr. Bhim Rao Ambedkar and his work for women and their rights in pre-India as well as post-independent India. And his views on the current social situation of India. The researcher tried to attempt a lot about Dr. Baba sahib about women empowerment in this paper and felt in need of secondary data also collected from the books, internet, journals, newspapers, thesis, and so on.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Gender equality, gender is the primary deprivation. Networking, leadership, and financial freedom are essential aspects of women's empowerment. Dr. Ambedkar realized this during his time and joined the social reform process. The concept of Dr. Ambedkar about women is clearly shown in the Indian constitution. Equality of sex is strongly supported by Dr. Ambedkar in articles 14, 15, and 16 in the Indian constitution. The principle of gender equality in the Indian constitution is based on its status, basic rights, basic duties, and directive principles, they laid the

base of social integrity, and without gender equality, there can be no social justice. In the paper of Dr. sahib on '*castes in India: his method, birth, and development*', Dr. Ambedkar described how women were treated cruelly through sati, widowed women were enforced and girl marriages were merely to maintain strict upbringing (endogamy) in one caste and social evils regarding women in Hindu and also Muslim religion as a researcher.

Dr. Ambedkar studied in his religion (and in other regions as well) about the difficult positions of downtrodden women in India and also highlighted this issue to maintain the status the men have. He said that the consequences of the system that veils Muslim women are that it deprives them of mental and moral mindset. Dr. Ambedkar says that Buddhism provides women equal status with men and is capable of associating women with spirituality. Adopting Buddhism, Dr. Ambedkar wiped out the injustice of unprivileged segments including women also for their equal status. Dr. Ambedkar refused to worship the Hindu deities, ultimately freeing women from inhuman customs, rituals, and superstitions and paving the way for her freedom

Root Cause of the Low Status of Women in Indian Society

Initially, women used to enjoy freedom, autonomy, and rights in Indian society. Women were considered important in the pre-Vedic period when societies were found to be matriarchal. With the advent of the Aryan or Vedic culture, the matriarchal society got replaced by a patriarchal society. However, women still had various rights and autonomy and had access to all sorts of learning opportunities. They had important roles to play in religious ceremonies and in selecting their life partners. They were able to study the Vedas and dare to cancel a marriage or remarry. Widow remarriage was also permissible. However, women's status deteriorated at the end of the Vedic period because of gender differentiation. From a socio-economic point of view, women have been cornered and deprived of their fundamental rights.[1] They had no autonomy or proprietary rights. The deterioration of their situation which started in the late stage of the Vedic period was aggravated by the imposition of strict rules on them by our legislator Manu.

Manu, in his book 'Manu smriti', 'codified all the social evils as social tenet instead of their eradication' (Kumar, 2016, p. 214). Under the influence of Manu smriti, women faced various hardships in the acquisition of property, education, and study of religious scriptures. The idea that women should not be liberated and enslaved to male domination has become outdated. The

Muslim invasion of our country and misuses such as the purdah system,[2] polygamy [3], and Talaak [4] further worsened the situation.

The British Raj in India provided new hope to Indian women. Educated and enlightened social reformers have sought to cleanse Indian society by freeing it from the shackles of social evil. Swami Vivekananda and Raja Ram Mohan Roy, went to great lengths to abolish Sati and supported the remarriage of the widows. Jyotibai Phule devoted his entire life to the education of women. Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar and Mahatma Gandhi had also struggled for women's cause (Kumar, 2016, p. 214). Dr. Ambedkar held Manu smriti responsible for the quandary of Indian women (Kavita Kait, 2013). He had faith in Buddha Dharma which nurtures equality, self-respect, and education for women (Das, 2015, p. 191).

The worldwide feminist goals of placing women on equal footing with men and securing their access to education, property, and participation in the political process are strikingly similar to Ambedkar's conception of women. When Ambedkar thinks it a crime to keep girls submissive to males, one might hear an echo of J. S. Mill's idea. Women, who make up half of the world's population, must be empowered if we are to envision a developed world devoted to human rights. Through his creative efforts, he spoke out against the social system that taught women obedience and drove them to stay subordinate to male dominance and conform to stereotypical feminine conduct. He believed in a link between caste and gender and stated that gender annihilation is a natural consequence of caste annihilation.

The fundamental reason that contributed to the establishment of caste, according to Ambedkar, was the growing distinctions between groups. Castes were exclusive castes that used endogamy to regulate women's sexuality. He condemned the caste-gender connection of being fully to blame for all forms of exploitation. His academic understanding, as well as his personal experience of being humiliated multiple times as a result of his social status, helped him to understand the relationship between caste and gender. Ambedkar thought that political democracy could only succeed if social democracy ensured a way of life-based on equality, liberty, and fraternity. As a significant start toward this goal, he recognized the critical need of ensuring women's rights and elevating their status and position. (Dhara, 2016)

The Education for Women

“The object of primary education is to notice that every child who enters the portals of a primary school does depart it only at a stage when it becomes literate and continues to be literate all over his life.” Dr. B R Ambedkar

Empowerment envelops building in the capacity of community individuals to develop and part of their mainstream society. Education is the only means by which societies rise from oppression to democratic participation. It is a powerful tool to empower individuals as well as women.

Ambedkar identified two objects of knowledge: first to achieve it for the betterment of others and also for the betterment and benefit of your purpose. Ambedkar also argued against proficient learning (British education system) aimed at creating a religious life for workers. Dr. Ambedkar also emphasized secular education for social liberty or freedom

The sole purpose of education is mainly to enlighten the downtrodden classes of people so that they can grow in every respect in the social, political, and economic manner. The social and moral philosophy of Dr. B R Ambedkar is mainly to inform the downtrodden people to change their thoughts and also previous behavior to move in the direction of unity and liberty through education. Education is treated as the best tool and remedy for eradicating the social evils mostly in backward areas of India. Ambedkar’s philosophy of education was mainly to inculcate the values of the core subject such as liberty, equality, fraternity, justice, and moral character among all boys and girls, religion, class, and caste of all regions.

Ambedkar programmed three components as objectives for policymaker

1. Education for women (Valeska, 2012)
2. Education as an instrument of substantive equality,
3. Recasting the aims and also purposes of education

Dr. Ambedkar measured education as an important tool for the freedom of women., which was not allowable to take education with lower castes. It is obvious from his words that he had great concern for women’s empowerment. Addressing the Second All-India Dejected Classes Women’s Conference held on 20 July 1942 at Nagpur, he said, *“I assess the progress of society by the degree of development which women have attained. I shall say to you a few things which I think you should tolerate in mind. Learn to be clean; keep free from all evils. Give education to*

your children. Impart ambition in them. Hammer on their minds that they are destined to be great. Remove from them all inferiority complexes.”

Thus Dr. B R Ambedkar stressed education for the people of India and also laid stress on women's education in the country with deep devotion and freedom. And advised providing education to your children (male/female) He wants them to realize that they owe a great responsibility to educating their children in the right way. He stresses the need for the nourishment of the mind and the spirit of self-help among men and women. He also advised them: to send their children to school. To him, education is the most significant factor in molding the life of all.

Ambedkar observes

“Education is equally necessary for women and men. If you were able to read and write, there would be a lot of progress. As you are, so your children will be righteously ruled in their lives, for the sons should be the ones who would make a mark in this world.”

B.R Ambedkar said that women want to help them out of their misery and economic dependence. He also demanded educational rights, equality, and also property rights for women. To give economic rights and freedom. To educate women he asked for coeducation for women with men. Through education, endured those women will think independently which leads to their intellectual and mental development.

Ambedkar's Reformative Measures and Initiatives in Elevating Women's Position

Ambedkar's much-reputed journals Mook Nayak and Bahishkrit Bharat became the forums to raise voices against gender inequality and the need for women's rights. There were three phases of women's program under the aegis of Ambedkar: women's contribution in the movements of the 1920s, along with men, such as the temple entry movements, the building of self-governing organizations for women in the 1930s and politically organizing women under the All-India Dejected Classes Mahila Federation in the 1940s. A conference of it organized in 1942 at Nagpur was attended by 25,000 women (Dhara, 2016). Women were greatly influenced by his speeches and thoughts. The launching of the 'Mahad Satyagraha' [5] in 1927, a blaze of 'Manu smriti' in 1927,[6] the Kalaram Temple Entry Satyagraha [7] in 1930, and the formation of the women's connotation in 1928 in Bombay were positive steps to organize and empower women so then they could fight to retrieve their social rights (Singariya, 2014, p. 2). He was successful in bringing a reflective change in their lifestyle. He wanted them to live a splendid life. Therefore, he

contended they do not wear clothes or curios that would indicate their low status. Child nurture be is a hard process, he advised women to buzzword from giving birth to many children and dedicate their time to other tasks (Dhara, 2016). Ambedkar emphasized the education of women, equal treatment with men, property right, and their involvement in the political process. He wanted to free them from age-old customs, rituals, and superstitions and therefore asked them to get rid of all orthodoxy and embrace modern values and develop a progressive perspective. He also included them in the process to eradicate castes. (Bakshi, 2017) Dr. Ambedkar a strong believer in the strength of women said:

I gauge a community's success by the amount of progress made by women. Let every bride-to-be stand for her husband, claim to be his friend and equal, and refuse to be his slave. I am confident that if you heed my advice, you will bring respect and glory to your stores. (Singariya, 2014, p. 2)

Being enthused by his thought in the Kalaram Temple Entry Satyagraha at Nasik in 1930, 500 women were arrested. Women formed their Samata Sainik Dal. Imbibed by the courage Ambedkar instilled in women, Radhabhai Vadale in addressing a press conference raised her voice in favor of women's rights and against all sorts of exploitation. Tulsibhai Bansole started a newspaper entitled Chokhamela. David, a mediator of a brothel, left his profession under the inspiration of his teachings. Ambedkar also fought against child marriage, prostitution, and the devadasi system (Singariya, 2014, p. 3). The year 1924 is especially substantial for women as in this year, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, as a member of the Bombay Legislative Council, advocated family planning and introduced the Maternity Benefit Bill. 'It is in the interest of the nation that the mother ought to get a convinced amount of rest during the pre-natal period' (Kumar, 2016, p. 396). Following the Madras Legislative Council in 1934 and other provinces passed the Maternity Benefit Act. Between 1942 and 1946, he was effective in bringing the Mines Maternity Benefit Bill for women in the entire country. In 1961, the central government passed a common Maternity Benefit Act for the whole country. He proclaimed that women should get equal earnings as men and brought the principle of equal pay for equal work. Article 39(d) provides this under directive principles of state policy.

He upheld voting rights for women. Ambedkar sturdily supported the education of women as he had the firm conviction that the education of women and men can prove a boon to the whole family (Ambeth, 2015). He also said, 'I am a great believer in women's organization. I recognize

what they can do to improve the condition of society if they are induced. In the eradication of communal evils, they have abridged great services' (Kumar, 2016, p. 397). The Indian Constitution pledges social and economic rights and justice to women, because of his extreme efforts. Mention may be made of the different articles which enable women to improve their status:

1. Article 14 guarantees that the state shall not deny to any person equality before the law and equal protection of the law within the territory of India.
2. Article 15 forbids discrimination based on religion, race, caste, gender, or place of birth.
3. Article 15 (3) enables the government to make positive discrimination in favor of women and children
4. Article 16 ensures equality of opportunity in public employment.
5. Article 23 Human trafficking and forced labor are both prohibited.
6. Article 39 (a) and (d) compel the state to give equal means of subsistence and equal remuneration for equal effort
7. Article 42 enjoins the state to provide arrangements for reasonable and humane working conditions, as well as maternity leave.
8. Article 51 A (e) imposes a basic obligation on every person to oppose acts that are damaging to women's dignity.
9. Article 243 D (3) requires that at least one-third of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in each panchayat be designated for women.
10. Article 243 T (3) makes a provision that not less than one-third of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every municipality shall be reserved for women. Article 243 T (4) provides reservations to the office of chairpersons in municipalities for Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe women. (Kumar, 2016, pp. 215–216)

The Hindu Code Bill of 1949 in the Constituent Assembly was one of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's most important contributions to women in raising and strengthening their dignity. It was a failed attempt to codify Hindu personal law. The fact that society was ruled by separate laws was a big issue for India in the post-independence days. It was the idea of two exceptional individuals, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar and Jawaharlal Nehru. The main argument behind the bill was to uplift the entire nation, including women. It sought to focus on two main objectives:

- (a) Upgrading the status of women and
- (b) Removing all disparities and inequalities.

It sought to put an end to the pervasiveness of different marriage systems and legalize only monogamous marriages (Katulkar, 2008). Property and adoption rights were conversed on women by the code, denied to them by Manu. In legal matters, equality was encouraged among men and women. Dr. Ambedkar said:

“I should like to draw the attention of the house to one important fact. Burke, the great political philosopher who published his major book against the French Revolution, remarked that those who desire to conserve must also be willing to restore. And all I ask of this House is that if you wish to preserve the Hindu system, culture, and society, you should not be afraid to mend what has to be repaired.

The bill seeks little more than the rehabilitation of damaged elements of the Hindu system.”
(Singaria, 2014, p. 3)

Ambedkar saw sacramental weddings as contrary to the spirit and philosophy of the Constitution, which imposes servitude on women. (Katulkar, 2008). The Hindu Code Bill incorporated the following:

- (1) The right of both male and female heirs to the property of a deceased Hindu who died intestate without leaving a testament.
- (2) The sequence of succession among the several heirs of a deceased dying person's possessions.
- (3) The law of maintenance
- (4) Marriage
- (5) Divorce
- (6) Adaptation
- (7) Minority & guardianship. (Kumar, 2016, p. 217)

A person's estate would be divided equally among his widowed wife, his son, and his daughter if he died. Previously, the daughter's property rights were refused. According to the measure, any property owned by a woman might be treated separately based on her choices. Both men and women would be able to file for divorce. In the event of a divorce, the husband would be compelled to support his wife. Monogamy would be made compulsory, and inter-caste marriage

would be permitted. A youngster with aspirations for any caste might be adopted. The high job of codifying Hindu personal laws had been assigned to India's first law minister after independence. A committee was formed under the chairmanship of Ambedkar, other members of the committee included K. Y. Bhandarkar, G. R. Rajagopal, and S. V. Gupta. However, the bill confronted strong confrontation from the orthodox Hindu society as this bill came as a foremost challenge to patriarchy. The bill was subjected to strong opposition from supporters of Hindutva, Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS), and Hindu Mahasabha. The bill was considered offensive to the 'Dharma shastra' and hostile to the Hindu culture. Before it could be placed in the Constituent Assembly, some sectors among the Hindus raised the slogan that Hinduism was in agony and threat. However, Nehru's cabinet approved it. But regrettably, it faced fervent opposition in the parliament from important personalities, namely, Sardar Patel, Syama Prasad Mukherjee, Pandit Madan Mohan Malviya, and Pattabhi Sitaramayya. This led Ambedkar to resign. However, it was finally approved in the parliament in 1955–1956 with the hope that it would revolutionize Indian society and culture. The four articles of the Hindu Code Bill that got assent and became laws in 1952 were the Hindu Marriage Act of 1955, the Hindu Succession Act of 1956, the Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act of 1956, and the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act of 1956 (Babare, 2016, p. 25).

The Hindu Marriage Act has been involved in bringing various changes in the Hindu marital law. It proved a great advantage to Indian women by emphasizing monogamy and providing relief in matrimony and maintenance even after divorce. Particularly significant are Sections 5, 11, 17, 25, and 26. Section 5 increases the age from 15 to 18 for a girl in case of marriage. Sections 11 and 17 of the acts enforce the rule of monogamy. The act provides for the nullity of marriage and divorce. Under Section 18 (2e) of the act, a Hindu wife can claim care. Section 26 of the act provides for custody of children [8]

Section 14 of the Hindu Succession Act of 1956 raises the position of a woman from a subordinate to a superior position in a matter of holding and disposing of her property (Mapping Women's Gains in Legacy and Property Rights under the Hindu Succession Act, 1956). As per Section 6a of the Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act, 1956, the custody of a minor who has not yet reached the age of 5 remains with her mother. The custody of an illegitimate boy or an illegitimate unmarried girl remains with the mother as per Section 6b. The mother is empowered

to modify and appoint a new caretaker as per Section 9 of the act.[9] The Adoption and Maintenance Act also empowers women and respects their decision in adopting a child.[10]

In his famous book, *Pakistan or The Partition of India*, Ambedkar articulated his concern about Muslim women wearing a veil, their religious traditions, and marriages and fought in contrast against all kinds of discernment against them (Babare, 2016, p. 25). He championed several legislations for women in India, including the Women Labor Welfare Fund, the Women Labor Protection Act, the Maternity Benefit for Women Labor Bill, and the Leave Benefit to Piece Workers Act. Employees' pay scales are being revised. Reintroduction of the Ban on Women Working Underground in Mines, maintenance allowance from spouse after legal separation, equal pay for equal labor regardless of gender, voting rights for women, adoption of a child by a widow, right over parental property, and marriage not before the age of 18.[11]

Relevance of Ambedkar's Contribution

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar emphasized rebuilding Hindu society based on equality. As law minister and head of the Drafting Committee, he imposed on himself the task to liberate women from the 'age-old thralldom' by rewriting Manu's social regulations. (Sing Ariya, 2014, p. 3). His writings and activities as a social reformer went a long way in the empowerment of women. The National Policy for the Empowerment of Women, 2001, admitted that social and economic structure is largely responsible for gender discrimination, as visualized by Ambedkar long ago (Shukla, 2011).

The government has undertaken several initiatives aimed at empowering women, as well as education for women, self-help groups, capacity building and skill development training, a focus on women and child development, employment opportunities, women's political participation, and the establishment of the National Commission for Women. (Kavita Kait, 2013).[12] Constructive steps have been taken by the 5-year plans to foster the development of women.

The state provides for positive discrimination. Positive Although Indian women have made some progress, still they face a variety of societal ills such as kidnapping, eye-teasing, violence, criminality, dowry, acid assaults, rape, and honor killing.[13] Rising incidents of harassment by spouse and other relatives, both in the father's house and in-laws' house, occupies the highest position as per data. Data also reveals that 46 percent of women are illiterates in India. It will take several decades to rectify the imbalances and discrimination A greater clamor for women's rights

shows that vast is undone. Although they have been empowered socially, economically, legally, and politically, there has been a dearth of adequate awareness regarding women's rights. They are not treated as equal to men (Tiwari & Meshram, n.d.). In India, there are two types of women's rights movements: one of the elite classes and the other of the downtrodden; the first influenced by Western thought and the other run by the workers for their rights.

There is a notable omission in that Ambedkar's ideas were not acknowledged in the first type of women's empowerment movement. In India, the feminist movement has been unsuccessful in addressing the concerns of lower caste women and has failed to give adequate attention to their rights. This exclusion is visible in the Vishakha Guidelines on sexual harassment at the workplace, which does not apply to the unorganized section. To stop sexual harassment at the workplace, a bill was passed in the Lok Sabha on 2 September 2012, entitled the Sexual Harassment at Workplace Bill. It became an act in 2013 and is named the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013. It incorporates the guidelines and norms suggested by our honorable Supreme Court in the Vishakha vs. State of Rajasthan Case.[14] Lower caste women comprising 70 percent of the unorganized sector are deprived of the privilege of enjoying equal compensation. Abolition of patriarchy and the caste system, the two deep-rooted evils of our society can only bring about emancipatory changes and prevent the reoccurrence of Nirbhaya (Sawant, 2015). Not only constitutional necessities but a change in the heart and attitude of people can liberate and brace women, the much-cherished goal of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar. A joint venture on part of women themselves and the government can remove all burdens on the way to their development

CONCLUSION

In a way, what appears in Ambedkar's perception of the Indian society between Hindus and Muslims was a system where women were denied their dues to society, in different ways. They were perplexed looking for solutions to their evil systems and tried to impose a society based on equality, justice, race, and fraternity. Although the goal of women's empowerment is yet to be achieved, Dr. Ambedkar's view of women's rights and development is still valid in the present scenario - not only in India but also in the global context.

Dr. Ambedkar's three-word formula- '*educate*' '*agitate*' and '*organize*', is a powerful tool for social change even today Ambedkar informed the oppressed and a lot of the miserable classes

of their rights which were denied to them for centuries. he thought, there is a way to inculcate in them a sense of consciousness, self-respect, and dignity. They wanted the people to cultivate values of freedom and equality among themselves; it was only possible through education.

Dr. Ambedkar was a symbol of knowledge and character. He considered education as a means of reaching the gates of light, and cognition and can remove the regions of darkness and ignorance. He used his philosophy of education to inform the state of social degradation in Hindu society among the lower class of society and to change social order for the benefit of the whole of mankind through their educational institutions; his institutes are working for the educational development of all. They were truly an 'organic intellectual'. Dr. Ambedkar's thinking about education made him an independent intellectual of the world. He promoted his philosophy of education and greatly influenced the outlook of downtrodden people. His statue is placed at the entrance gate of the London school of economics to honor his brilliant academic career and is a symbol of "below.

Knowledge "is written. It shows how he was acclaimed as a brilliant student and far-off excellent educator. Dr. Ambedkar's views on education and his educational viewpoint are still relevant for the social economic and political development of our country in the 21st century and will work again. "Unless you achieve social freedom, whatever freedom is provided by law is of no use to you.

Dr. B R Ambedkar, India's first law minister Sir we the people of India salute you for your great efforts and immense work. *"A great man is different from an eminent one in that he is ready to be the servant of the society"* minister Eknath Shinde

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Notes

1. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's newspaper Mook Nayak or The Mute Hero became instrumental in raising the cause of the untouchables in 1920. Sanskrit Bharat or India Ostracized was started in 1927 (Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's Caravan, 2015).
2. Purdah is a social and religious practice in Muslim society that symbolizes the non-inclusion of women.
3. Polygamy is the practice of having more than one spouse by a man or a woman (<http://www.dictionary.com/browse/polygamy>).
4. Talak is a divorce in the Muslim community which is affected by the husband's repudiation of the marriage and his enunciation of the word (<http://www.duhaime.org/LegalDictionary/T/Talaq.aspx>).
5. Mahad Satyagraha led by Ambedkar paved the way for the untouchables to use water in Mahad, a public tank (Harad, 2017).
6. As a protest against the discrimination that women faced under the influence of our Dharmashastras (Manu Smriti), a bonfire of Manu smriti was held by Ambedkar in front of 50 women (Barnwell, 2014).
7. The Kalaram Temple Entry Satyagraha was held in 1930 in Nasik, in which 500 women participated (Babare, 2016).
8. Hindu Marriage Act, 1955. Retrieved from http://www.highcourtchd.gov.in/hclsc/subpages/pdf_files/4.pdf
9. Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act, 1956. Retrieved from http://www.ncpcr.gov.in/view_file.php?fid=423
10. The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956. Retrieved from <http://tcw.nic.in/Acts/Hindu%20adoption%20and%20Maintenance%20Act.pdf>
11. Dr. Ambedkar and Labor Day. Retrieved from <https://dramedkarbooks.com/2016/04/30/dr-ambedkarand-labour-day/>
12. National Commission of Women, a statutory body, was constituted in 1992 under the National Commission for Women Act, 1990, to ensure legal and constitutional safeguards for women to seek redressal of various grievances and make policy suggestions (National Commission for Women, 2017, <http://ncw.nic.in/>).

13. The killing of a woman in the name of honor when she dares to choose her life partner against the accepted social mores, is a step taken to punish her collectively by the family and the community (Haile, 2007).
14. See Vishakha Guidelines (2010, November 4). Retrieved from <http://www.iimb.ac.in>

REFERENCES

- Babare, S. (2016). Dr. B. R. Ambedkar and women empowerment in India. *Research Front*, 4(1), 23–26.
- Bakshi, S. (2017, April 4). Ambedkar on women. Retrieved from <http://www.dailyexcelsior.com/ambedkar-on-women/>
- Barnwal, K. B. (2014). Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's quest for gender equality is relevant in contemporary feminist discourse. *International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, IV (11), 393–400.
- Das, S. (2015). Ambedkar and women rights: An analysis. *International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary and Multidisciplinary Studies*, I(I), 191–195.
- Dhara, L. (2016, April 14). Ambedkar's understated feminism. *Forward Press Magazine*. Retrieved from <HTTPS://www.forwardpress.in>2016/04>
- Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's Caravan. (2015). Mook Nayak and Bahishkrit Bharat. Retrieved from <https://drambedkarbooks.com/tag/mooknayak-and-bahishkrit-bharat/>
- Ambeth. (2015, March 4). Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar and Women's Rights in India. Retrieved from <http://www.ambedkarambeth.blogspot.in/2015/03/progress-for-society-is-measured-by.HTML?m=1>
- Haile, J. (2007). Honor killing. Its causes and consequences: Suggested strategies for the European Parliament. Human Rights, Policy Department, External Policies. Retrieved from [www.europar.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.HTML?reference=EXPO-JOIN_ET\(2007\)385527](www.europar.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.HTML?reference=EXPO-JOIN_ET(2007)385527)
- Harad, T. (2017, March 20). The significance of Mahad Satyagraha: Ambedkar's protest March to claim public water. *Feminism in India*. Retrieved from <https://feminisminindia.com/2017/03/20/mahad-satyagraha/>
- Katulkar, R. (2008, August 31). Dr. Ambedkar on women's liberation. Retrieved from <http://www.countercurrents.org>Katulkar3108>
- Kavitakait. (2013, December 18). Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's role in women's improvement. *Law articles: India's most authentic free legal source online*. Retrieved from <http://www.legalservicesindia.com/article/article/dr-b-rambedkar%E2%80%99s-role-in-women-empowerment-1611-1.html>
- Kumar, B. (2016). Liberating Indian women from slavery: An analysis of Dr. Ambedkar's contribution to uplifting Indian women's rights. *International Journal of English Language, Literature and Humanities*, IV(I), 212–219.

- Mapping Women's Gains in Inheritance and Property Rights under the Hindu Succession Act. (1956). Lawyers' collective women's rights initiative. Retrieved from <https://docplayer.net/19363816-Mapping-women-s-gainsin-inheritance-and-property-rights-under-the-Hindu-succession-act-1956-lawyers-collective-women-s-rightsinitiative.html>
- Sawant, C. (2015, April 14). Women should understand Dr. Ambedkar's teachings. The Free Press Journal. Retrieved from <http://www.freepressjournal.in/mumbai/women-should-understand-dr-ambedkars-teachings/565508>
- Shukla, D. (2011, October 24). Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's vision toward gender equality. Retrieved from <http://www.lawyersclubindia.com/articles/Dr-B-R-Ambedkar-Vision-towards-Gender-Equality--4144.asp>
- Singariya, M. R. (2014). Dr. B. R. Ambedkar and women empowerment in India. *Quest Journals, Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 2(1), 1–4.
- Tiwari, R., & Meshram, S. H. (n.d.). Dr. Ambedkar's contribution to women's development. *Academia*. Retrieved from http://www.academia.edu/11998296/Dr._Ambedkar_s_contribution_to_women_development